

Supplemental Table S3 Top 20 enriched GO terms MF

Category	Term	Count	%	PValue	Genes	List Total	Pop Hits	Pop Total	Fold	Enrichment	Bonferroni	Benjamini	FDR
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	chaperone binding	8	5.97014925	1.19E-05	FGB, DNAJB6, TFRC, DNAJA4, TIMM9, TBCD, CLU, CP	132	110	18811	10.3641873	0.003824619		0.003831929	0.003808202
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	extracellular matrix structural constituent	8	5.97014925	5.14E-05	FGB, EFEMP1, LUM, COL14A1, FGG, BGN, AEBP1, THSD4	132	138	18811	8.26130874	0.016474421		0.008305603	0.008254175
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	extracellular matrix structural constituent conferring compression resistance	4	2.98507463	1.73E-04	VCAN, LUM, BGN, ASPN	132	16	18811	35.6268939	0.054343833		0.018623801	0.018508483
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	unfolded protein binding	7	5.2238806	3.11E-04	CCT6A, HSP90AB4P, DNAJB6, NACA, DNAJA4, CLU, CLGN	132	131	18811	7.61490863	0.095588716		0.025113859	0.024958356
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	RNA binding	23	17.1641791	5.04E-04	EIF5A, RPL4, RPS9, PNPT1, TFRC, COL14A1, HDLBP, C4BPA, PA2G4, IFIT1, ILF2, RPL3L, ARCN1, CCT6A, RBM3, EFTUD2, PRPF6, IFI16, PUF60, U2AF2, TRIP6, MYO18A, DHX15	132	1470	18811	2.22971037	0.150339462		0.032575459	0.032373754
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	cadherin binding	8	5.97014925	0.006704	LASP1, SNX2, PUF60, PPP1R13L, PACSIN2, HDLBP, PARK7, LRRFIP1	132	316	18811	3.60778673	0.886129746		0.360900753	0.358666073
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	collagen binding	4	2.98507463	0.0119012	LUM, COL14A1, AEBP1, ASPN	132	68	18811	8.38279857	0.979082043		0.54915565	0.545755305
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	double-stranded RNA binding	4	2.98507463	0.015483	TFRC, DHX15, LRRFIP1, ILF2	132	75	18811	7.60040404	0.993527183		0.625127995	0.621257233
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	protein homodimerization activity	11	8.20895522	0.027416	STAT5B, SNX2, TFRC, TIMM9, XPNPEP3, CAT, LPL, PARK7, LRRFIP1, FBLN5, TYMP	132	713	18811	2.1985741	0.999873973		0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	ryanodine-sensitive calcium- release channel activity	2	1.49253731	0.0275686	RYR1, RYR3	132	4	18811	71.2537879	0.999880202		0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	calcium-induced calcium release activity	2	1.49253731	0.0275686	RYR1, RYR3	132	4	18811	71.2537879	0.999880202		0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	transcription coactivator activity	6	4.47761194	0.0345307	PRPF6, CTBP2, WBP2, NACA, CTBP1, PARK7	132	258	18811	3.31412967	0.999988237		0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	heparin binding	5	3.73134328	0.034734	CLEC3B, LPL, F2, SOD3, KNG1	132	176	18811	4.04851067	0.99998901		0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	protein binding involved in protein folding	3	2.23880597	0.0360901	CCT6A, DNAJB6, CLGN	132	43	18811	9.94238901	0.999993021		0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	structural constituent of muscle	3	2.23880597	0.0360901	SMTN, CSRP2, NEXN	132	43	18811	9.94238901	0.999993021		0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	calcium ion binding	11	8.20895522	0.0374189	RYR1, CLEC3B, VCAN, EFEMP1, LPL, PLS3, F2, FBLN5, RYR3, ASPN, CLGN	132	752	18811	2.0845523	0.999995531		0.722976524	0.718499889

GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	oxidoreductase activity, acting on peroxide as acceptor	2	1.49253731	0.0410687	CAT, PARK7 RPL4, TFRC, TACO1, HDLBP, F13A1, C4BPA, PARK7, IFIT1, LCLAT1, CLU, GLS, EFTUD2, PREX1, EFEMP1, KPNA4, KPNA3, RPS9, USP7, SACM1L, ANK2, ILF2, PRPF6, SOAT2, MYADM, PHPT1, PFKFB2, NLRX1, RAB5C, CTBP2, PSMD14, CTBP1, LPL, AK4, FBLN5, KNG1, HPX, PSMD14,	132	6	18811	47.5025253	0.99999869	0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	protein binding	98	73.1343284	0.0418199	XPNPEP3, TPP1, PARK7 RYP1, AKAP12, AEBP1, MYH10, RYR3	132	12539	18811	1.11378439	0.999998983	0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	peptidase activity	4	2.98507463	0.042528		132	111	18811	5.13540814	0.999999199	0.722976524	0.718499889
GOTERM_MF_DI RECT	calmodulin binding	5	3.73134328	0.0552484		132	205	18811	3.47579453	0.999999989	0.767603158	0.762850197
